

The P versus NP problem. Refutation.

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Abstract

In the article we provides an response to the problem of equality of **P** and **NP** classes, which is also called the Millennium problem. As a result, given the complete result of equality. For theory of refutation we use method of "reductio ad absurdum". We use tensor analysis for define objects which considered relatively to the Turing machine computation. The goal was to give an answer to a problem that has affected to degree of the proof calculation's details. The result can be obtained relative to the current problems of equality **P** and **NP** classes, but other than that give an opportunity to explore the computational process more.

1 Introduction

The problem of problem of equality of **P** and **NP** classes as well as many math problems has many solutions. Like for many mathematical problem, for this problem there is one true solution and other solutions can be described.

We will do without consideration concrete works and just consider the abstract description of the statements that are false. False mathematical solution of problem of equality of **P** and **NP** classes can be summarized as follows statement: imagine that there is an object relative to which classes **P** and **NP** are not equal, since such object exists, the class is not equal. For us is not important which kind of object referred in such statements and how this object determined. It is only important for us the train of such statements.

The statement that there is an object relative to which the classes **P** and **NP** are not equal, along with classes inequality asserts the existence of such an object. However, since such object exists relative to class inequality, correspondingly, classes have to be any way unequal for the existence of such object. For us, this approach may look false for many reasons. However, we will focus on only one.

Since classes inequality determined a priori as a true, for us, this approach says very little about the nature and presupposition of this equality. However, nature of, presupposition of problematics, equality of classes **P** and **NP** seems to us as major problem of their relations. This brings us to the need to choose such an approach of solving the problem, that equally admit there equality and inequality, and the answer to the problem by which would be the way of there mathematical proof.

2 Method

As the right approach in our proof, we use the method of "reductio ad absurdum". A similar method was used by Aristotle and Bourbaki gives a formal definition of the method in his work "Theory of Sets" [1, Chapter 1, p. 33]. At the same time, we rely on the theory of Gödel's incompleteness theorems that would identify this kind of absurd for us.

According to the method of "reductio ad absurdum", we construct our theory as follows. First, we assume the equality of classes **P** and **NP**, then we get an object of this assumptions - *CIV* space 6, after that we correlate with *CIV* space objects which define classes **P** and **NP** 3 and we get an absurdity 7 which determines the equal relation between classes **P** and **NP** for us.

The space *CIV*, that we get on the second stage of our theory, is possible to get and use through the incompleteness of mathematics. Since mathematics is incomplete, that any derivative of its objects should also comply to this property. This allows us to correlate objects that define classes with space derived from their assumptions.

3 Definitions and Alphabet

Let repeat the main definitions given by Stephen Cook in article "THE P VERSUS NP PROBLEM" [2] in short.

Let Σ be a finite alphabet (that is, a finite nonempty set) with at least two elements, and let Σ^* be the set of finite strings over Σ . Then a language over Σ is a subset L of Σ^* . For each string ω in Σ^* there is a computation associated with M with input ω .

The language accepted by Turing machine M , denoted $L(M)$ by

$$L(M) = \{\omega \in \Sigma^* \mid M \text{ accepts } \omega\} \quad (1)$$

Denote by $t_m(\omega)$ the number of steps. For $n \in \mathbb{N}$ we denote by $T_M(n)$ the worst case run time of M ; that is,

$$T_M(n) = \max\{t_M(\omega) \mid \omega \in \Sigma^n\} \quad (2)$$

M runs in polynomial time if there exist k such that for all n , $T_M(n) \leq n^k + k$. Class languages **P** is

$$\mathbf{P} = \{L \mid L = L(M) \text{ for some Turing machine } M \text{ that runs in polynomial time}\} \quad (3)$$

Checking relation $R \subseteq \Sigma^* \times \Sigma_1^*$, with which associate a language L_R over $\Sigma^* \cup \Sigma_1^* \cup \{\#\}$ defined by

$$L_R = \{\omega\#y \mid R(\omega, y)\} \quad (4)$$

R is polynomial-time iff $L_R \in \mathbf{P}$. **NP** class of languages defined by condition that language L over Σ is in **NP** iff there is $k \in \mathbb{N}$ and a polynomial-time

checking relation R such for all ω ,

$$\omega \in L \Leftrightarrow \exists y(|y| \leq |\omega|^k \text{ and } R(\omega, y)) \quad (5)$$

where $|\omega|$ and $|y|$ denote the lengths of ω and y , respectively.
After repeat main definition introduce a little lemma:

Lemma 3.1. $\Sigma^* \neq \Sigma$.

Proof. Let $\Sigma^* = \Sigma$, then language L from Σ^* will be equal language L from Σ . That contradict to the definition of L . \square

4 Classes equality

For equality of classes \mathbf{P} and \mathbf{NP} must be fulfilled condition of equality,

$$A = B \Leftrightarrow \forall x : (x \in A) \Leftrightarrow (x \in B) \quad (6)$$

which implies that is

$$\mathbf{P} = \mathbf{NP} \Leftrightarrow \forall L(M) : (L(M) \in \mathbf{P}) \Leftrightarrow (L(M) \in \mathbf{NP}) \quad (7)$$

That mean, that should be that kind of language L_{civ} which can be defined as a strong \mathbf{NP} and \mathbf{P} at the same time,

$$L_{civ} = L(M) \text{ for some Turing machine } M \text{ that runs} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{in polynomial time} \wedge \omega \in L_{civ} \Leftrightarrow \exists y(|y| \leq |\omega|^k \text{ and } R(\omega, y))$$

where $|\omega|$ and $|y|$ denote the lengths of ω and y , respectively.

5 Determination of computation

To discover equality $\mathbf{P}=\mathbf{NP}$, consider the process of Turing machine working as a process with an already predetermined outcome.

In other words, present the process of calculation in an environment where all possible languages previously was computed and all true results already predicted. That can't contradict with definition of Turing machine or with any definitions from chapter 3, because working process and machine structure stay the same. Changed only presupposition of machine for possibility of fully predetermined computation outcome before any computation step, which made possible for us that considering.

By true result, we mean an accepted result of computing ω in the best case run time for M .

In that case, we can denote a three-dimensional computing coordinate system and define the language L as a matrix in computing coordinates.

Remark. It will be true to note, that for each machine must exist its own coordinate system and considering the computation language without machine relativity unacceptable. As noted earlier, for the theory, we consider such conditions of machine environment that allow us to make known the correct for best case run presets and considered computation regardless of machine particularity.

Figure 1: computing coordinate system with calculation basis

The dimension of this system defined by number machine calculation step — $step$, point in time — m and the value from the alphabet — ω .

So, now we can denote the language L as a matrix,

$$L = \begin{pmatrix} step_1 & step_2 & \cdots & step_n \\ m_1 & m_2 & \cdots & m_n \\ \omega_1 & \omega_2 & \cdots & \omega_n \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

After we determine the language matrix, we can denote the computation of an language L as a valence tensor (m, ω) ,

$$Computation_{j_1 \cdots j_m}^{i_1 \cdots i_\omega} = \sum_{\substack{k_1, \dots, k_m \\ h_1, \dots, h_\omega}}^3 \cdots \sum_{h_1}^3 S_{h_1}^{i_1} \cdots S_{h_\omega}^{i_\omega} T_{j_1}^{k_1} \cdots T_{j_m}^{k_m} \widetilde{Computation}_{k_1 \cdots k_m}^{h_1 \cdots h_\omega} \quad (10)$$

Computation of L_{civ} is equal irrespectively to 7,

$$(L_{civ} \in \mathbf{P}) \Leftrightarrow (L_{civ} \in \mathbf{NP}) \rightarrow \mathbf{P}_{m_{civ}}^\omega = \mathbf{NP}_{m_{civ}}^\omega \quad (11)$$

6 Computation equality

From equality condition of tensors it follows, that there should be a basis, relative to which all components of the tensor are equal. That basis for $\mathbf{P}=\mathbf{NP}$ equality we named CIV .

It is important to say, that the basis CIV is temporary object which exist as exist equality of $\mathbf{P}=\mathbf{NP}$. CIV 's analytical definition allows us to use it without predetermination basis space which can or can't exist. So, that possible to

suppose that computation space where $\mathbf{P}=\mathbf{NP}$ is a space which specify by the basis CIV .

Defining a basis CIV , we can express the calculation of any language L in space where $\mathbf{P}=\mathbf{NP}$ by replacing the main calculation basis for CIV ,

$$L = \begin{pmatrix} step_1^{civ} & step_2^{civ} & \cdots & step_n^{civ} \\ m_1^{civ} & m_2^{civ} & \cdots & m_n^{civ} \\ \omega_1^{civ} & \omega_2^{civ} & \cdots & \omega_n^{civ} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c_{1,1} & c_{2,1} & \cdots & c_{n,1} \\ c_{1,2} & c_{2,2} & \cdots & c_{n,2} \\ c_{1,3} & c_{2,3} & \cdots & c_{n,3} \end{pmatrix} \quad (12)$$

Replacing matrix of $c_{n,3}$ have the same temporary nature as basis CIV . That allow us express the calculation without definition anything about replacing matrix. Also, we don't definition of calculation basis for prof $\mathbf{P}=\mathbf{NP}$ equality.

7 Refutes of equality

Corollary 1. *Since the existence of the language L consisting from any ω is possible, it is possible to chose that language, for such expression ω to space specified by CIV is*

$$\omega^{civ} : (\omega^{civ} \in \Sigma^*) \Leftrightarrow (\omega^{civ} \in \Sigma) \quad (13)$$

As mentioned before, we don't strictly define the space where $\mathbf{P}=\mathbf{NP}$, but we strictly define ω in chapter 3. That make following outcome acceptable for us.

Corollary 1 as came from 12 contradict to Lemma 3.1 and fully refutes equality $\mathbf{P}=\mathbf{NP}$ Q.E.D.

8 Conclusion

The axiomatic result of corollary 1 that classes \mathbf{P} and \mathbf{NP} are not equal is intuitive in many ways. Intuitively, it can be formulated as follows: not all objects that were equally formed equal.

However, if the task of mathematics would be calculation the right answers, it would be impassible to imagine how from the addition of oranges we have reached the \mathbf{P} versus \mathbf{NP} problem.

References

- [1] Nicolas Bourbaki. *Theory of Sets*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2004.
- [2] Stephen Cook. The p versus np problem. *The millennium prize problems*, pages 87–106, 2006.